

Current Capability of SIMMER-V Code to Simulate Severe Accident Transients in 3D Geometry

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ABSTRACT

The SIMMER-V code, developed in cooperation between France and Japan, aims at simulating severe accident transients in 3D geometry in SFRs. Continuous improvement of performance and stability of the code enables now SIMMER-V to run complete ULOF sequences in much shorter computer times than before, i. e. some days compared to months previously. After describing the parallelization approaches currently developed in SIMMER-V, two examples of transients, with and without power excursions, are given and commented.

Keywords: Sodium Fast Reactor, Severe Accident, SIMMER-V, Simulation

1. INTRODUCTION

The SIMMER-V code, currently developed in cooperation between France and Japan, aims at simulating, in Sodium cooled Fast Reactors, severe accident (SA) transients from the initial core steady state to generalized degradation situations in which large molten pools could form, power excursions may occur as well as debris discharge towards a core catcher [1], [2].

In SIMMER-V, originally based on the SIMMER-III/SIMMER-IV code system approach, new physical models and numerical capabilities were developed and combined:

- A detailed fuel pin model that is able to represent thermo-mechanics of irradiated fuel, fission gas release and in-pin molten fuel dynamics [3]
- A capability to describe the complete isotope vector for each fuel type in the core (i. e. fissile with different burn-ups and fertile blankets) [4]
- Domain decomposition and boundary coupling techniques that enable to take advantage of high performance computing environments and tackle with demanding 3D computations [5].

Severe accident transient simulations require to take into account the coupling between multiphase thermal-hydraulics, structure degradation and spatial neutronics. In several studies, the core has been described in 2D geometry (e. g. based on the approximate cylindrical symmetry of the core) in order to reduce the computational burden of the simulations. The simplification however results in trends that are partly overconservative (due the artificially enhanced coherency of the degradation pattern) and partly underconservative (e. g. due to the cylindrization of transfer tubes). The possibility to run the cases in 3D geometry is therefore necessary if reasonable uncertainties on essential features of the SA (e. g. energetics of power excursions, flow rate of debris towards the core catcher) have to be established.

Due to recent progress in reactor core design to increase safety, potential unprotected transients are less energetic and so large core degradation and debris discharge are observed later, compared to previous core designs. Thus, more than 200 s of degradation progress may be necessary for the simulation of severe accidents in new core designs, where ~30 seconds could be enough with previous core designs. Combining such complex and intricated processes in 3D numerical simulations over such long sequences requires to upgrade significantly the code numerical performance, considering that previous

2D and 3D core degradation simulations could last from several weeks to several month computing time.

This paper presents the approaches undertaken to enhance the numerical performance of SIMMER-V compared to previous versions of the code and illustrate how this performance enhancement enables to represent complete severe accident transients on realistic cases.

In a first part, the operator splitting approach of SIMMER-V will be recalled. The different parallelization levels of the code will then be described and code scalability discussed. Two examples of application will then be presented before conclusion of the paper.

2. THE OPERATOR SPLITTING APPROACH OF SIMMER-V

2.1. Overview of the SIMMER-V approach

The SIMMER-V code solves on a Cartesian finite volume mesh the multicomponent-multiphase compressible Navier-Stokes equations, mass and energy conservation equations, equations describing the thermal state and stability of structures (e. g. cladding, fuel pellet, canwall, control rod) and the equations accounting for neutron transport and flux evaluation in transient conditions.

No global implicit numerical scheme exists for representing such a complex set of phenomena and an operator splitting approach is therefore used to elaborate a resolution path. In this approach, different parts of the physics are solved separately within a time step and combined in such a way that the numerical error resulting from the splitting operation remains small.

The neutronics part, together with density and temperature fields provided by thermalhydraulics (TH), evaluates cross sections and uses an improved quasistatic (IQS) method [6] to determine the flux shape and amplitude and feeds back the TH with the spatial power distribution. Based on the IQS method, flux amplitude, varying rapidly, is evaluated more frequently than flux shape. The TH part is split in four successive operations [6] in order to complete a TH time-step:

- STEP1 evaluates in-cell heat and mass transfer and phase change, momentum exchange coefficients, interfacial areas, structure configuration
- STEP2 performs convection of mass, energy and momentum
- STEP3 computes the pressure field
- STEP4 evaluates interfacial area convection and makes final adjustments

2.2. Time step constraints

Due to the operator splitting approach, efficient time step control is necessary to limit the error. In the TH part, when conditions are smooth (i. e. no violent phase change or heat transfer), time step is mainly controlled by a CFL (Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy) condition. For example, during the computation of reactor steady state, time step magnitude is typically in the range of 10^{-3} s.

Figure 1: Time step hierarchy during coupled thermalhydraulics/neutronics simulations in SIMMER-V. Δt^f : fluid time step (TH), Δt^r : reactivity time step, Δt^s : flux shape time step.

Additional constraints on the time step magnitude may apply in order to limit energy and mass transfers or pressure changes within a TH time step in order to ensure convergence. During transient situations, depending on the stiffness of phenomena, the TH time step usually evolves between $5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ and 10^{-4} s. In the same way, the time interval for reactivity and flux shape evaluation in the neutronics

part will depend on conditions. When evaluating permanent state of reactor starting from initial cold conditions, reactivity time step and shape time step may take large values. In severe transients (e.g power excursions with significant fuel movement or vaporization), both reactivity and shape time steps have to be reduced in the range of 10^{-7} s to 10^{-4} s. The time step hierarchy in SIMMER-V is schematized in Figure 1. Code embedded criteria enable SIMMER-V to adjust the different time intervals shown in Figure 1 so that operator splitting errors remain small. However, situations like strong power excursions require care and attention and may require to strengthen the constraints on time step magnitude limitation.

3. PARALLELIZATION APPROACHES IN SIMMER-V

3.1. Parallelization approach in the thermalhydraulics/degradation part

Within the TH part, the main target for computational performance improvement is the STEP1 part, in which intracell interfacial area source terms, momentum exchange functions, and heat and mass transfer are determined. In general, STEP1 accounts for ~90 % of the computing time of the TH in a sequential run for typical reactor calculation. Inside STEP1, the part dedicated to the evaluation of vaporization/condensation heat and mass transfers (VCHMT) is found to represent more than 70 % of STEP1.

Because STEP1 is a procedure in which most quantities are evaluated locally, a domain decomposition method (DDM) has been developed for the TH part of SIMMER-V. The whole spatial domain is divided into several (up to several hundreds or thousands depending on the mesh size) independent subdomains which are computed in parallel. The other parts of the TH part (STEP2, STEP3 and STEP4) also benefit from the DDM approach despite their lower scalability.

Communications between the different subdomains is ensured by the Message Passing Interface (MPI) standard [7] thanks to a layer of overlapping ghost cells at the border of each subdomain. Each subdomain is therefore managed by an independent MPI task.

In addition, the MPI parallelism described above has been hybridized with shared memory parallelism inside each subdomain thanks to the OpenMP library [8]. In this case, several computational threads can run simultaneously using data in a shared memory region.

Feedback from different runs shows that, in SIMMER-V, the use of hybrid MPI/OPENMP brings significant benefit on performance for run configurations with 2 to 4 OPENMP threads combined with at least 64 MPI tasks. Note that this observation is partly dependent on the computing node architecture, in particular data transfer buses and memory organization inside the sockets.

Figure 2: Evolution of the speed-up of different parts of the thermalhydraulics of SIMMER-V as a function of the number of MPI tasks. The data were obtained on a test case with a ~100 000 mesh spatial grid. Left: Speed-up of the VCHMT part of STEP1. Right: compared speed-ups of STEP1 and STEP2. (Speed-up = ratio of time duration of the sequential run to the parallel run)

Figure 2 illustrates how the speed-up (i. e. the ratio of time duration of the sequential run to the parallel run) evolves for different parts of the thermalhydraulics of SIMMER-V as a function of the number of MPI tasks.

The VCHMT part exhibits a superscalar behavior probably due to cache memory effects. On the other side, the STEP2 has a rather poor performance. The different parts of thermalhydraulics show some heterogeneity in their performance and globally the thermalhydraulics speed-up may reach values ~ 250 for typical cases decomposed in 500 to 1000 subdomains. Figure 3 illustrates how hybridizing MPI and OpenMP parallelization approaches may bring up to 50 % more performance for the same number of cores.

Figure 3: Illustration of the benefit of MPI/OPENMP hybridization in SIMMER-V thermalhydraulics. In the example given here, the pure MPI run (256*1) computes 256 subdomains in parallel. The optimal hybrid run (64*4) uses the same number of cores but computes only 64 subdomains in parallel; each subdomain is using 4 OpenMP threads. The optimal case runs ~ 50 % faster than the pure MPI case.

3.2. Parallelization approach in the neutronics part

Shared memory parallelism (OpenMP) is implemented in the angular sweeps of neutron transport (based on the THREEDANT solver) of the standard SIMMER-V version. The speed-up brought by this implementation is moderate (2 to 4). Investigations have been conducted to set-up in SIMMER-V similar approaches explored for SIMMER-III/SIMMER-IV [9], by using a DDM parallelized transport solver; in this case, speed-up in the range of 10 is obtained. The part of the code dedicated to cross section evaluation is also a target for parallelization as it may represent an important part of the global calculation cost during power excursions.

Investigations have also been conducted in order to evaluate the possibility to offload computation of flux shape on GPU computers. It has been shown that this approach would require rewriting all of the original source code to comply with the specific development features that allow to benefit from the whole GPU acceleration potential. It is therefore concluded that in future efforts of performance improvement, the best solution is not to modify the existing neutronics solver but to replace it by another module.

4. SELECTED EXAMPLES OF SA TRANSIENTS SIMULATED WITH SIMMER-V

4.1. Configuration of runs

The cases presented in this section were run with SIMMER-V v2024 which is the latest official version of the code. The code can be compiled either in INTEL20 or GNU12.3 environment. Optimization level of the Fortran compiler was set to $-O1$. OPENMPI 4.1.4, PETSC3.15.0 and HDF5/1.12.0 libraries were used to compile the code. The IRENE/ROME cluster at TGCC was used to run the cases. Each computing node, based on 2 AMD Rome processors, has 128 cores with 1.8 GB RAM/core. An Infiniband HDR100 interconnection network ensures the communications between nodes.

4.2. Simulation of an ULOF transient on a CFV-type core

An ULOF (Unprotected Loss of Flow) transient on a CFV-type (low void effect) core was first performed in 2021, using the a preliminary version of SIMMER-V [10]. In 2025, the same calculation was performed using the SIMMER-V v2024 version. This calculation lasted 10 days, compared to more than a month of calculation time in [10], highlighting the notable increase in SIMMER-V's computational performances over the past five years.

The CFV core type (Figure 4) is characterized by :

- An inner core, composed of heterogeneous axial structures, including an inner fertile plate and a significant sodium plenum at the top of the subassemblies.
- An outer core, with a longer homogeneous fissile column structure, and consequently a slightly smaller sodium plenum, than the inner core.

Figure 4 : CFV type core structure. Left : in the axial cut. Right: in radial cut. The radial cut shows the location of the 18 Transfer Tubes (3 in the center, 15 at the periphery). The core is represented in a 3D Cartesian mesh that maps the original hexagonal subassembly network.

The core design also includes 18 so-called Transfer Tubes (TT) (Figure 4) which are intended, after melting of their canwall, to enable the transfer of core debris from the degraded core region directly to the core catcher region. The simulation starts with a stabilization phase of 90 s of permanent state, followed by a 205 s ULOF transient. Figure 5 presents the time evolution of both normalized power (P/P_0) and reactivity during the transient phase. For clarity purpose, the permanent state and the first 20 s of the ULOF phase have not been represented.

Figure 5: Time evolution of normalized power (P/P_0) and reactivity. Main events : 1- beginning of Na boiling, 2- sodium reflux, 3- beginning of pin degradation, 4-combined effect of sodium reflux and material degradation, 5- first break-up of a CRGT (Control Rod Guide Tubes) wall. For the sake of clarity, the 90 seconds of permanent state have been omitted from the graphs.

As observed on the Figure 5, power (and reactivity) first exhibits a rather linear decrease (- 35%) due to neutron leaks at the upper part of the heated sodium plenum (part 1). Then, between approximately 140 and 150 s (part 2), power and reactivity oscillations are observed. The latter are due to sodium vaporization/condensation at the top of fuel assemblies. Sodium boiling, caused by the reduction of the coolant flow, induces a reduction of the reactivity and therefore a lower power. Combined with the thermal inertia of structures, this promotes sodium condensation which reduces neutron leakage. Reactivity and power increase again and this starts another power oscillation until dry-out of cladding occurs. At around 160 s (part 3), pin degradation is observed, producing further oscillations in

power/reactivity, which then are due to simultaneous pin degradation (promoting steel and fuel movement) and sodium vaporization/condensation (part 4).

At approximately 190 s of simulation (part 5), canwall of a first Control Rod Guide Tube (CRGT) breaks and this leaves, radially and axially, some space for fuel debris to escape and therefore decreases core reactivity. The power continues to decrease, until reaching approximately $P/P_0 = 0.03$ at 285 s.

Figure 6 : Evolution with time of the number of subassemblies showing sodium boiling (□), degraded subassemblies (Δ) and open CRGTs (◇).

As seen in Figure 6, a maximum of 250 boiling subassemblies (out of 291) is obtained, at 185 s (i. e. 95 s after the ULOF onset). The number of degraded CRGTs is 10, at the end of the simulation (i. e. 205 s after the ULOF onset).

4.3. Simulation of an ULOF transient on a reactive core

In order to explore the capability of SIMMER-V to simulate situations with power excursions and more extreme phenomena, the previous core design was modified (reduction of sodium plenum) in order to increase the core reactivity and the spatial coherence of the degradation (by modification of power/coolant flowrate ratio).

Figure 7: Reactivity evolution during the ULOF transient. Left (90 s to 175 s): 1- coolant heat up in the sodium plenum, 2- onset of sodium boiling (outer core), 3- first pin degradation in the outer core, 4- onset of sodium boiling (inner core), 5- first subassembly degradation (inner core), 6- first canwall breaking, 7- first CRGT break-up, 8- 2nd CRGT break-up, 9- 4 broken CRGTs, 10- 8 broken CRGTs. Right (170 s to 207 s): massive decrease of reactivity is clearly visible after the last power excursion at 191.5 s.

Figure 7, Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the results obtained during the ~120 s of ULOF transient that were computed in 9 days computing time. Computation time is equally shared between thermalhydraulics

and neutronics. Due to the provoked enhanced spatial coherence of degradation, large fuel pools are formed. Oscillations and sloshing of fuel pools trigger several large power pulses between 185 s and 192 s. Eventually, after the transfer of large fuel masses through the transfer tubes (Figure 4) towards the core catcher region, reactivity drops down to very negative values.

Figure 8: Left: normalized power in log scale. Right: evolution of fuel masses in selected parts of the reactor.

Figure 9: Left : Axial cut of the core at 191.5 s, showing on the left a Transfer Tube. Right: color code for materials on the left part of the figure.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The results presented in this paper show that significant progress has been made in the numerical performance and stability of the SIMMER-V code dedicated to the simulation of severe accident transients of SFRs. The simulation of complete degradation sequences, from the initiating phase to the stage of mitigation is now possible in less than ~10 days in 3D geometry. This new capability opens the way to better analyze the different mitigation configurations that can be achieved depending on core design and different hypothesized unprotected transients.

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